

D.4.3.4. Report on risk assessment and modelling of animal Coronavirus evolution.

JIP COVRIN WP4

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REPORT ON RISK ASSESSMENT AND MODELLING OF ANIMAL CORONAVIRUS EVOLUTION

1. Introduction

COVRIN aims to integrate research by One Health EJP partner institutes on the topics of SARS-CoV-2 emergence, risk assessment and preparedness. The project has two main operational objectives: (i) to identify drivers for the emergence and spread of SARS-CoV-2, and (ii) to generate data and build models for risk assessment of SARS-CoV-2. To achieve these objectives, integrative research activities are focused on four topics:

- (i) Research on detection of SARS-CoV-2 in animal species and the environment;
- (ii) Research on SARS-CoV-2 molecular and biological characterization;
- (iii) SARS-CoV-2 surveillance and risk assessment, focussed on the animal human interface; and
- (iv) coronavirus preparedness.

The overall aim of the COVRIN project is to generate and share data of these integrative research activities, in order to increase the preparedness for future coronavirus outbreaks.

The WP 4 aims to investigate the coronavirus preparedness through the study of virus – host interactions, potential of virus evolution and host adaptation.

2. Description of the task

The objective in subtask 4.3.4 is to investigate the application potential of data and research outcomes generated within COVRIN for virus emergence and evolution risk assessments to finally help to improve surveillance and control strategies.

In this subtask, data from COVRIN WPs 1, 2, 3 and 4 were analysed on their potential to be integrated into future risk assessments, e.g. on the question which animal species/conditions offer the highest potential for future virus emergence. This work includes

- i) the definition of a One Health risk assessment framework that is capable of assessing risks originating from zoonotic hazards in an integrated One Health approach, and
- ii) an overview on how specific results from the COVRIN project and other publicly available resources could contribute to such a One Health SARS-CoV-2 risk assessment.

3. Definition of a One Health risk assessment framework:

A literature review was performed to identify the most appropriate risk assessment framework to perform truly integrated One Health compliant risk assessments as needed for hazards like SARS-CoV-2. Some frameworks have been developed to assess the risk of potential zoonotic hazards to various populations (animals, plants, humans) [21, 44–46]. Usually the risk assessment of zoonotic diseases focus on the risks originating from the transmission potential zoonotic pathogens from the animal reservoir to humans, mainly through direct transmission or through food consumption. [1, 5, 33, 36].

The currently established risk assessment frameworks are mainly designed for domain-specific risk assessment questions. For example, the OIE risk assessment framework was designed primarily to assess the risk for animals and humans from the import of animals and animal products. The Codex Alimentarius framework is used to assess the risk for humans from consumption of food products. There are also some tools that help to select the appropriate risk assessment framework. Among other tools, we can cite the COHESIVE Decision Support Tool for One-Health Risk Assessment [14]. This tool offers support to decide on which risk assessment framework to use depending on the risk assessment question, the expected risk assessment outcome and the available calculation capacities and data.

Unfortunately, the complexity of risk assessments on SARS-CoV-2 evolution in animals and the risks originating from that for animal and human populations goes beyond what established frameworks support. Specifically, the aspect of coronavirus evolution implies that:

- i) The sources of animal exposure to the virus are multiple including the risk for multiple occurrences,
- ii) The virus can survive in the environment and re-contaminate animals or humans,
- iii) the virus virulence and epidemiological characteristics can change through virus mutations,
- iv) The human exposure can occur through multiple pathways (direct animal to human, from the environment, through contaminated food from plants or animal origin).

Due to this complexity in the hazard characteristics and the interconnections between the different pathways of exposure, any risk assessment of the animal coronavirus evolution should be performed within a holistic One Health risk assessment framework. Using one of the existing frameworks would be not sufficient to catch all the complexity of the risk assessment question.

Therefore, we developed a One Health risk assessment framework, combining concepts from the OIE, the Codex Alimentarius and the Environmental chemical contaminants risk assessment frameworks. Here it is important to mention that some guiding documents can help in assessing the risk of one health hazard. For example, the tripartite, World Health Organization (WHO), Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE), have recently published a Joint Risk Assessment Operational Tool. This tool offers resources that help to address the risk of zoonotic diseases in countries in a One Health framework.

4. Risk assessment framework to assess the risks related to animal coronavirus evolution

The risk of animal coronavirus evolution and the risk for future pandemics requires to assess the potential of SARS-CoV-2 introduction and evolution in various animals and the risk for transmission to humans. To address these questions, the risk assessment needs to cover:

- coronavirus introduction, maintenance, and evolution in various animals
- spread of coronavirus variants either directly, through the environment, or through food products to humans and other animals
- human exposure, hazard and risk characterisation

4.1. Coronavirus risk assessment framework elements

The proposed framework for assessing the risk of coronaviruses evolution is structured in 5 steps (see: RA framework COVRIN Project.jpeg):

A. Hazard identification:

This step aims to identify the hazard (coronavirus and its different strains here) capable of causing adverse health effects in sensitive hosts, animals and humans, which potentially could be exposed. At this step, questions about the hazard investigated, and its characteristics need to be answered:

- ✓ Are there evidences that the hazard poses a potential risk to animals or to humans?
- ✓ How is the hazard of concern associated with the hosts of interest: humans +animals?
- ✓ What is the likelihood of the hazard causing adverse effects: public health, economical and animal welfare?
- ✓ What adverse health effects could be associated with the exposure of the different hosts?
- ✓ What are the susceptible hosts?
- ✓ What are the hosts and pathogens characteristics that could affect the type and severity of the adverse effects?
- ✓ How do common exposure pathways link the adverse effects with the hazard?
- ✓ How often occurs the hazard in animals?

- ✓ How do environmental conditions influence the hazards transfer, evolution, fate along the exposure pathway?
- ✓ Are there measures implemented or could be implemented that reduce the risk of exposure or limit the adverse effects?

B. Hazard ecology assessment:

Description of the biological pathways necessary for the animal coronavirus to be introduced in animal host populations, the potential evolution of the virus while spreading in different animal species or in a particular environment, and estimation of the probability of that complete process occurring. Here we need to ask about:

- ✓ What are exposure sources for animals?
- ✓ What is the probability that wild or domestic animals get exposed from humans?
- ✓ What is the probability that wild or domestic animals get exposed from environment or contaminated materials?
- ✓ What is the probability of transmission between the different animal hosts?
- ✓ What is the prevalence of the disease in the different hosts and sources?
- ✓ What is the probability of virus evolution while spreading in different animal species?

C. Exposure assessment:

At this step, we have to describe the pathways leading to the exposure of the target populations to the coronavirus released from different sources. It is also necessary to estimate or describe the probability of the exposure occurrence. Key questions to be investigated here are:

- ✓ What is the probability of spread from infected animals to the target population (humans or animal species of interest)?
- ✓ Can the virus survive in the environment?
- ✓ Can humans and animals get exposed through vegetables, water, feed or direct exposure in the environment?

D. Consequences assessment:

Description of the relationship between exposures to different strains of coronavirus, original strains or mutated, in different hosts (human or animals) and consequences of those exposures. A causal process must exist by which exposures produce adverse health or environmental consequences, which may in turn lead to socio-economic consequences. The consequence assessment describes the potential consequences of a given exposure and estimates the probability of these consequences occurring. This step would have to answer questions about:

- ✓ What does the virus evolution imply in terms of disease dynamics change, adaptation to new species and humans, change in virulence characteristics, ...?
- ✓ What are the consequences for humans getting exposed to different strains?
- ✓ What are the consequences for companion animals getting exposed to the different strains?
- ✓ What are the consequences for wild animals getting exposed to the different strains?

E. Risk estimation:

At this step, outcomes from the previous risk assessment steps are combined to produce an overall measure of the risk associated to animal coronaviruses evolution.

5. Contribution of the COVRIN project deliverable to coronavirus risk assessment

The figure “COVRIN project findings in the developed risk assessment framework.jpeg” shows how findings and deliverable produced within the COVRIN project could feed future risk assessments on animal coronavirus evolution. The different work packages outputs [2–4, 6–11, 13, 15, 17–20, 22–26, 28–32, 34, 35, 37–43] are here linked to the different Coronavirus risk assessment steps within the developed framework, where the different results from the COVRIN project contribute to answer the questions and concepts addressed.

The outcomes focusing on host's susceptibility to SARS-CoV-2 infection, both in field studies and experimental infection challenges (ST1.1.1 [30], 1.1.2 [30], 2.3.2 [29], 3.4.2 [17], 3.4.3 [18], 3.4.4 [19], 4.3.1 [32], and 4.3.3 [11]), are of great interest to identify what animal species are potential hosts for the virus. Combined to findings from other work investigating the transmission of the virus between animals (ST2.4.3 [4], 3.4.4 [19], and 3.4.5 [20]), this allows to better understand the potential of spreading among animals that SARS-CoV-2 could have. In addition, ST1.3.1 [38] detected SARS-CoV-2, in fomites and aerosols in real life setting and in food, surfaces, and water in experimental settings. ST1.3.2 [38] estimated the infectivity of the virus over time in different environments. These findings are useful to understand and estimate the role of the environment in the virus transmission between animals and potentially to humans. ST 3.4.2 [17] and 3.4.4 [19] through investigating the efficacy of vaccines and the persistence of protective antibodies in animals are important to assess the role of Human intervention to limit the virus spread among animals.

In ST2.4.2, an antigenic cartography was developed. This result allowed to compare antigens over variants. These findings can be used to further investigate and predict the difference in antigenic characteristics of future evolutions of the virus. This result profit from the findings of ST 2.3.3 on host - virus interaction to better understand the infection process and predict the effect of future recombinants of the virus. In addition, findings from ST1.1.3 [38], 2.1.1 [22], 2.1.2 [25], 2.2.1 [42], 2.3.2 [29], and 3.4.4 [19], aim to collect and harmonize diagnostic tools. These outcomes will be essential to ensure standardization and comparability of future studies on host susceptibility to SARS-CoV-2 and comparability between prevalence studies. Moreover, ST3.1.2 [7] collected SARS-CoV-2 surveillance data and described limiting factors for surveillance. The surveillance of animal coronavirus would allow to enrich future risk assessments with knowledge about animal outbreaks and recombinants, infection prevalence and geographical distribution of virus variants.

Some other research results and tools external to the COVRIN project might also be useful in future risk assessments on animal coronavirus evolution. These resources were collected under the ST4.3.4. branch of the Mindmap. For example, CovidOutcome2 [27] is a machine learning based tool for SARS-CoV2 mutation identification and for disease severity prediction in humans. This tool can be useful to assess the consequences of human exposure to different SARS-COV2 strains. Other tools, like Pyro-cov [16] or deepchain [12], can be used to predict future mutations of the coronavirus. Therefore, these tools can feed the introduction/release assessment step of the risk assessment.

6. Perspectives

The developed framework here can be enriched to provide a generic risk assessment framework to investigate the risk of pathogenic agents in a one health approach. A generic risk assessment framework is needed for hazards that imply complex interactions between humans, animals, and their environment. Especially when human and animal hosts, multiple pathways and different exposure processes are involved, the use of the domain-specific risk assessment frameworks becomes difficult.

Mapping the COVRIN project findings and their potential integration in the different steps of the risk assessment is an essential task for future risk assessment. Such mappings need to be maintained and further enriched with findings and data from external and future projects. These resources mapping could make risk assessment tasks faster and guide risk assessors in selection of the most appropriate approaches to adopt.

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